

Influence of Environment on the Force Constants of 10^{-4} Ion*

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The influence of cations and crystal symmetry on the force constants of 10^{-4} ion has been discussed in the light of Orbital Valence force field, General Valence force field and Urey Bradley force field. The symmetry force constants thus obtained are compared with those obtained by kinetic constants approximation and L-matrix approximation. It is inferred that the effect of substitution of various alkali cations appear to decrease the bending force constants and to increase the non-bonded repulsion.

Recently, Seibert¹ has reported the vibrational analysis of 10^{-4} ion in a number of alkali matrices and hydrated salts, with a view to examine the influences of cations and crystal fields (symmetry) on the spectrum. In this communication we have presented a comparative study of the applicability of different force fields to the tetrahedral 10^{-4} ion. Different force fields used are Orbital Valence force field², Urey Bradley force field³ and General Valence force field⁴. Orbital valence force field has been successfully applied to a number of molecules and ions by the authors during recent years⁵⁻⁷.

The tetrahedral 10^{-4} ion has its vibration distributed⁸ as $\Gamma = A_1 + E + 2F_2$ i.e., one vibration each of A_1 and E type with two degenerate F_2 type. Unlike other methods⁹⁻¹¹ where several constraints are placed to overcome the difficulty of obtaining unique set of symmetry force constants for a given symmetry species involving $(1/2)n_j(n_j+1)$ quantities from n_j observed frequencies of the species, O.V.F.F. is free from such approximations. Thus Orbital Valence force field provides an opportunity to test the validity of the various approximations used for the solution of the secular equations of higher order than one.

Method of Computation

Orbital Valence force field has been applied without assuming any relation between interaction constants. Symmetry coordinates given by Muller and Krebs⁴ has been used to evaluate modified U.B.F.F. constants following L-matrix approximation. Another set of force constants has been evaluated from kinetic energy constants¹². The symmetrised force constants related to the frequencies ν_3 and ν_4 are—

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_3 + \lambda_4 &= F_{33} G_{33} + 2F_{34} G_{34} + F_{44} G_{44} \\ \lambda_3 \lambda_4 &= \begin{vmatrix} F_{33} & F_{34} & G_{33} & G_{34} \\ F_{43} & F_{44} & G_{43} & G_{44} \end{vmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

These equations can be solved with the help of third equation involving kinetic constants as—

$$\frac{F_{34}}{F_{44}} = \sqrt{2} \cdot \frac{(K_{aa} - K'_{aa})}{(K_a - K'_{aa})}$$

* Dedicated to Prof. Santi R. Palit on the occasion of his 60th birth anniversary.

where K_{da} , K'_{da} , K_a , $K'_{a\alpha}$ are the kinetic constants corresponding to the potential energy constants. For details of the method of evaluation of these constants one is referred to the earlier work by Sanyal and Dixit¹³ and Thirugunasambandam¹⁴. The equations connecting the symmetry matrix elements and force constants in the three force fields are given below :

Symmetrised Constants	O.V.F.F.	U.B.F.F.	G.V.F.F.
$A_1 : F_{11}$	$k_1 + 8A$	$K + 4F$	$fr + 3frr$
$E : F_{22}$	$1/3(k\alpha + 2A + B/R)$	$H - 1/3F' + 1/3F$	$f\alpha + f'\alpha - 2f\alpha\alpha$
$F_2 : F_{33}$	$[k_1 + (8/3)A - (4/3)B/R]$	$K + 4/3(F + F')$	$fr - frr$
F_{34}	$(2/3)(2A - B/R)$	$(2/3)(F + F')$	$\sqrt{2}(f\alpha - f'\alpha)$
F_{44}	$(1/2)[k\alpha + (4/3)A + (10/3)B/R]$	$H - 5/2F' + 1/3F$	$f\alpha - f'\alpha$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The force constants as obtained with the application of O.V.F.F., G.V.F.F. and U.B.F.F. (tables 2 and 3) reproduce the observed frequencies reasonably well. The symmetrised force constants for F_2 symmetry species (table 3), obtained with the help of kinetic constants are comparable with those of O.V.F.F. which involves no any relation among symmetry force constants. Further the values obtained by L-matrix approximation are in agreement

TABLE 1
Vibrational frequencies (in cm^{-1}) of IO_4^- ion under different Alkali matrices

Systems	$\nu_1(A_1)$	$\nu_2(E)$	$\nu_3(F_2)$	$\nu_4(F_2)$
LiIO ₄	812	304	863	392
NaIO ₄	785	291	843	375
KIO ₄	796	278	853	345
RbIO ₄	796	272	854	335
CsIO ₄	791	269	844	309
AgIO ₄	751	286	799	312
NH ₄ IO ₄	792	275	847	325
Li(IO ₄) 3/2 H ₂ O	798	277	836	344
CO(NH ₃) ₆ (IO ₄) ₃ H ₂ O	797	280	856	339

with the force constants obtained by other methods confirming the validity of the approximations made in the former. Similar results have been obtained by the authors in their earlier studies^{12,13}. The bending symmetry force constants F_{44} obtained in all the cases comes out to be greater than the interaction constant F_{34} which is in agreement with the conclusion arrived by Thakur¹⁵ in case of BF_4^- and has been accepted by Müller⁴ *et al.* also.

It is evident from the table 2 that stretching force constants (k_1 or K) and bending force constants ($k\alpha$ or H) show changes characteristic of crystal lattice environment. It reasonably appears that the changes in force constants, though very small, are affected by the replacement of one alkali by another in the crystal field. The bending force constants and the stretching force constants both decrease continuously. This indicates an increase

TABLE 2
O.V.F.F. and U.B.F.F. force constants of IO_4^- under different crystal lattices

Systems	k_1 or K	$K\alpha$ or $3H$	$2A$ or F	$(-B/R)$ or F'	Force Fields
LiIO_4	6.192	0.836	0.004	0.030	O.V.F.F.
	5.733	0.869	0.120	0.122	U.B.F.F.
NaIO_4	5.981	0.735	-0.043	0.105	O.V.F.F.
	5.537	0.713	0.067	0.153	U.B.F.F.
KIO_4	5.829	0.618	0.035	0.074	O.V.F.F.
	5.694	0.687	0.069	0.110	U.B.F.F.
RbIO_4	5.893	0.618	0.020	0.059	O.V.F.F.
	5.696	0.658	0.069	0.108	U.B.F.F.
AgIO_4	5.229	0.685	0.022	0.064	O.V.F.F.
	4.925	0.768	0.097	0.100	U.B.F.F.
$\text{Cs}(\text{IO}_4)$	5.654	0.878	0.150	-0.045	O.V.F.F.
	5.536	0.712	0.090	0.060	U.B.F.F.
NH_4IO_4	5.734	0.620	0.045	0.047	O.V.F.F.
	5.426	0.824	0.144	0.043	U.B.F.F.
$\text{Li}(\text{IO}_4) \cdot 3/2 \text{H}_2\text{O}$	5.570	0.841	0.108	0.078	O.V.F.F.
	5.426	0.824	0.144	0.042	U.B.F.F.
$\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6(\text{IO}_4)_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	5.866	0.774	0.030	0.067	O.V.F.F.
	5.706	0.698	0.070	0.111	U.B.F.F.

but not regular in the non-bonded repulsion which is presumably due to the existence of Vander Waals forces depending primarily on purely distance effect between non-bonded atoms. This is complicated due to the presence of coulombic forces. It is expected that the ion IO_4^- residing in the environment of alkalis will be more perturbed due to heavier atoms and the order followed by alkalis and hydrated salts in the present case is valid. Therefore, we may conclude that the perturbation effect of alkalis crystal lattices tends to decrease bending force constants and increase non-bonded repulsions.

Comparing the stretching force of ClO_4^- and BrO_4^- ions with IO_4^- ion, it is observed that $f_r(\text{Cl-O}) < f_r(\text{Br-O}) < f_r(\text{I-O})$ and so is the case with bending. The symmetry force constants as evaluated with the help of kinetic constants agree very well with those of O.V.F.F., G.V.F.F. and U.B.F.F. and are capable of reproducing the vibrational frequencies

($F_2 \times F_2$ species) with equal accuracy. It is interesting to note that in the case of O.V.F.F. we get negative values of F_{34} which is objectionable. This may be the limitation of the model to explain with crystal frequencies. The negative values of F_{34} have been reported in literature¹⁷ but not in case of O.V.F.F. Also greater values of B/R as compared to A also, show the break down of the model. A large number of oxoanions¹⁶ have been subjected

Symmetrised force constants of IO_4^- ion (in mdyne/Å) under different crystal lattices

TABLE 3

Sytems	$F_{11}(A_{1v})$	$F_{22}(E)$	$F_{33}(F_2)$	$F_{34}(F_2)$	$F_{44}(F_2)$	Force Fields
LiIO ₄	6.210	0.290	6.156	-0.175	0.371	O.V.F.F.
	6.214	0.290	6.056	0.161	0.562	U.B.F.F.
	6.215	0.290	5.286	0.147	0.487	G.V.F.F.
NaIO ₄	5.808	0.266	6.064	-0.085	0.529	O.V.F.F.
	5.808	0.266	5.831	0.121	0.420	U.B.F.F.
	5.808	0.266	4.094	0.142	0.332	G.B.F.F.
KIO ₄	6.109	0.254	5.778	-0.026	0.445	O.V.F.F.
	5.972	0.243	5.935	0.125	0.435	U.B.F.F.
	5.972	0.243	6.034	0.103	0.239	G.V.F.F.
RbIO ₄	5.972	0.239	5.839	-0.026	0.414	O.V.F.F.
	5.956	0.232	5.932	0.182	0.411	U.B.F.F.
	5.956	0.232	5.083	0.118	0.205	G.V.F.F.
CsIO ₄	5.048	0.177	5.512	-0.140	0.313	O.V.F.F.
	5.897	0.227	5.777	0.100	0.349	U.B.F.F.
	5.897	0.227	5.028	0.114	0.268	G.V.F.F.
AgIO ₄	5.316	0.264	5.434	0.028	0.457	O.V.F.F.
	5.316	0.257	5.189	0.132	0.458	U.B.F.F.
	5.316	0.257	4.471	0.132	0.308	G.V.F.F.
NH ₄ IO ₄	5.912	0.252	6.266	-0.001	0.403	O.V.F.F.
	5.912	0.237	5.834	0.111	0.386	U.B.F.F.
	5.912	0.237	5.037	0.120	0.281	G.V.F.F.
Li(IO ₄) 3/2 H ₂ O	6.135	0.378	5.609	0.030	0.588	O.V.F.F.
	6.002	0.241	5.675	0.124	0.433	U.B.F.F.
	6.002	0.241	5.112	0.122	0.286	G.V.F.F.
Co(NH ₃) ₆ (IO ₄) ₂ 2H ₂ O	5.987	0.300	6.180	0.024	0.510	O.V.F.F.
	5.987	0.246	5.947	0.121	0.420	U.B.F.F.
	5.987	0.246	4.094	0.141	0.332	G.V.F.F.

to Orbital Valency force field studies where it fails to give correct picture of no-bonded repulsion A and the Lenard-Jone approximation $A = 6.5 B/R$ also breaks down.

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